

Development of Modeling Video Learning Media to Improve Self-Development Skills Clothing for Children with Retardation Mental at Yamet CDC

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to develop learning media for video modeling of self-development material for children with mental retardation at Yamet CDC Lampung. This research is based on the results of observations at school with an analysis of the need for development to overcome the problem of self-development in dressing children with mental retardation. The research method used was adapted from research and development (R&D) Borg & Gall, in its implementation the researcher only carried out until the 6th step, namely: (1) Potential and problems; (2) Data collection; (3) Product design; (4) Design validation; (5) Design revisions, and (6) product trials. Data collection techniques using observation, interviews, questionnaires, and documentation. The results of the analysis conducted in this study indicate that the conditions and potential availability of facilities and infrastructure strongly support the development of video modeling learning media for self-development skills in dressing children with mental retardation. The data analysis technique in this study used descriptive statistical analysis techniques. The results of validation by material experts got a total of 87.49% with very valid criteria, while the results of validation by media experts got a score of 80.55% with valid criteria. The results of product trials by the teacher got a score of 88.88 % with very decent criteria, while the results of field trials to students got a score of 89.69 % with very decent criteria. Based on the results of the responses from these students, it was concluded that the Video Modeling learning media could be implemented to improve dressing skills for mentally retarded children at Yamet CDC Lampung.

Keywords:- *development; modeling video; self-development skills; retardation mental.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The basic needs of mentally retarded children are self-development skills that have benefits for mentally retarded children, namely increasing the child's independence and reducing dependence on others. With intellectual limitations and the potential possessed by mentally retarded children, resulting in them being less able to meet their needs. They are also less able to socialize with their environment, less able to work or create jobs. Basically they lack the necessary life skills so that mentally retarded children are able to live independently.

Clothing is a primary need for humans. Dressing is very beneficial for humans both in terms of beauty, modesty, and health. Children with mental retardation also need to dress to take care of themselves. In normal children in general, fully clothed can be done independently at the age of 5 years. But it is different with mentally retarded children who have many obstacles in themselves. Seen from the lack of children's ability to take care of themselves. Even though the ability to take care of yourself is very important as a provision for independence in life. The self-development program is part of an educational program given to mentally retarded children to improve motor skills and self-confidence so that mentally retarded children can carry out daily life activities well without having to wait for help from others.

Gagne in Yusufhadi Miarso (2004), states that educational media are various types of components in the learner's environment that can stimulate students to learn. Meanwhile, Briggs argued that learning media is a means to provide stimulation for the learner so that the learning process occurs. Furthermore, Yusufhadi Miarso (2004) states that learning media are everything that is used to channel messages and can stimulate the thoughts, feelings, concerns, and willingness of students so that it can encourage a deliberate, purposeful and controlled learning process. So that the media is an important means for teachers to deliver learning that can improve students' understanding in the learning process.

Video Modeling is a form of video recording about someone who is doing a certain activity or behavior. The video recording was then shown to the subject, then the subject was given the opportunity to show behavior that

was in accordance with what was shown in the recording (Bellini & Akullian, 2007). The purpose of providing video modeling learning media is for children to only focus on the stimulus in the video so as to produce a good response in modeling activities. Based on this background, the title of the research to be carried out is:

- Analyzing the potential and conditions for the development of Video Modeling media in improving self-development skills in dressing for mentally retarded children at Yamet Child Development Center Lampung.
- Analyzing the development of Video Modeling media in improving self-development skills in dressing for mentally retarded children at Yamet Child Development Center Lampung.
- Analyzing the process of developing Video Modeling in improving self-development skills in dressing for mentally retarded children at Yamet Child Development Center Lampung.
- Analyzing user responses to video modeling media development products in improving self-development skills in dressing for mentally retarded children in Lampung.

II. METHOD

A. Type Of Research

The research and development method used in this research is Research and Development (R&D) or often called development (Sugiono, 2015) is “a research method used to produce certain products, and to test the effectiveness of these products”. The research and development steps according to Sugiyono include the following steps: (1) potential and problems, (2) data collection, (3) product design, (4) design validation, (5) design improvement, (6) testing product, (7) product revision, (8) trial use, (9) product revision, and (10) mass production. The researcher only implemented the 6 steps of Sugiyono’s Research and Development (R&D) until stage (6). This was done due to limitations, both in terms of time and cost. This research was conducted at Yamet Child Development Center Lampung.

B. Research Place

The place for this research is Yamet Child Development Center Lampung.

C. Research Subjects and objects

The research subjects are students with mental retardation. While the object of this research is the video modeling media in the material for self-development of clothes.

D. Data Collection Techniques

Research and development of video modeling learning media with material on dressing skills using observation, interviews, questionnaires, and documentation techniques.

E. Data Analysis Techniques

Researchers or developers collect data by using descriptive percentage analysis techniques. Quantitative data from product assessments that have been developed

during product trials were analyzed by descriptive analysis of percentages. Analysis of the data used to analyze descriptive data is to use a percentage interval scale.

The data analyzed in this study are: (1) Media expert validation questionnaire related to the quality aspect of content and objectives, instructional quality aspects and technical quality aspects with 4 answer choices according to the content of the question, (2) Media expert validation questionnaire related to text writing aspects, said or language, design, coloring aspects of graphic aspects and audio-visual aspects, and (3) Questionnaire validation of responses and user responses related to aspects of appearance, presentation, programming, and content. Each validation questionnaire has 4 answer choices according to the content of the question, with the answer choices having different scores which mean the level of validation of Video Modeling learning media development.

Score	Category
4	Very good
3	Well
2	Not good
1	Very Not Good

Table 1: Expert Validation Scores

Data from the questionnaire in this study used quantitative data to be analyzed descriptively by percentage with the steps according to Riduan (2004: 71-95) as follows:

- Calculating the value of respondents and each aspect or sub variable
- Recap values
- Calculating the average value
- Calculate the percentage with the formula:

$$DP = \frac{n}{N} \times 100$$

Information:

DP = Descriptive percentage (%)

n = Empirical score (score obtained)

N = Ideal Score for each question item

The results of the assessment scores from each material expert validator, media expert were then averaged and converted to determine the validity and feasibility of Video Modeling learning media. The following is the eligibility criteria for the average analysis shown in Table 2.

Persentase Skor	Criteria
81.25 < DP ≤ 100	Very Valid/Very Eligible
62.50 < DP ≤ 81,25	Valid/Eligible
43.75 < DP ≤ 62.50	Invalid/Inappropriate
25 < DP ≤ 43.75	Invalid/Invalid

Table 2: Validation Criteria

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the study using video modeling learning media to improve self-development skills to dress mentally retarded children at Yamet Child Development Center Lampung are as follows:

A. Potential and Conditions

The conditions and potentials at Yamet Child Development Center Lampung are quite good for the development of Video Modeling learning media, due to the availability of adequate information and communication technology facilities and infrastructure. As well as teachers who are technology literate and have appropriate educational backgrounds and are qualified in using learning media based on computer technology and Android. The link between the potential and the conditions that occur, it is necessary to develop a Video Modeling learning media to improve self-development skills in dressing for mentally retarded children at the Yamet Child Development Center.

B. Data and Information Collection

The results of the data analysis of the learning conditions of mentally retarded children at the Yamet Child Development Center have the potential to develop Video Modeling learning media. So the next step researchers find research literature related to the learning media that will be developed.

C. Product Design

The researcher carried out the next stage after collecting data and information and then designing the design. In planning the design Analyzing Core Competencies (KI), taking into account: KI-4. Demonstrate what is known, felt, needed, and thought through language, music, movement, and work in a productive and creative way, and reflects the behavior of children with noble character. And analyzing basic competencies:

- Demonstrate polite behavior as a reflection of noble character
- Using limbs for gross and fine motor development
- Able to help yourself to live healthy.

D. Desain Media

The development of learning media Video Modeling is made using Adobe Premiere and Adobe Flash software. The following is a display of the results of the design of learning media products:

a) Media Initial View

Fig. 1: Initial display of learning media

b) Registration display

Fig. 2: Registration display

c) Main Menu Page Display

After the user selects the gender correctly, the user will then enter the main menu page. On this page there are menus that can be accessed as shown in the following figure:

Fig. 3: Main Menu Page Display

d) Learning Material Menu Display

Fig. 4: Learning Material Menu Display for Girls

Fig. 5: Learning Material Menu Display for Boys

E. Design Validation

The development of learning media Video Modeling is made using Adobe Premiere and Adobe Flash software. The following is a display of the results of the design of learning media products:

a) Design Validation by Material Expert

The results of material expert validation with an average score of 87.49% with very valid/very feasible criteria, it can be concluded that the development of the Video Modeling learning application for dressing self-development skills can be used in self-development materials for children with mental retardation.

Aspect	Score	Category
Content quality and purpose	91.66	Very Valid/Very Eligible
Instructional quality	83.33	Very Valid/Very Eligible
Average score	87.49	Very Valid/Very Eligible

Table 3. Material Expert Validation Results

b) Design Validation by Media Expert

The results of media expert validation got an average score of 80.5% with valid/decent criteria. It can be concluded that the development of Video Modeling learning media can be used to improve the dressing skills of mentally retarded children.

Aspect	Validator		Average score	Category
	1	2		
Technical Quality	77.77	83.33	80.55	Very Valid/Very Eligible

Table 4: Media Expert Validation Results

F. Design Revision

Suggestions or input for improvement from material experts and media experts are as follows:

- Dubbing sound in the video is removed because it can interfere with children's concentration
- Instructions for use are improved in terms of sentence effectiveness and accuracy of word use

- The speed of the video is adjusted to the material, the video that is displayed is too fast so students will have difficulty following it.

After getting advice and input from material experts and media experts, and then the next step is to revise the design, following the results of the design revision:

- Improve learning video media by removing dubbing
- Improve usage instructions with more effective sentences and use words according to EYD
- Improved the speed when displaying video by slowing down the motion of the model in the video by increasing the length of the video.

G. Product Trial

The descriptive average percentage in the display aspect scored 86.57 with the criteria of "Very Eligible", in the presentation aspect it got a score of 89.50 with the "Very Eligible" criteria, in the programming aspect it got a score of 93.05 with the "Very Eligible" criteria, and the content aspect got a score of 89.53 with the criteria of "Very Eligible". So that the total descriptive average score of the percentage obtained is 89.68 with the "Very Eligible" criteria.

Aspect	Score	Category
Appearance	88.88	Very Valid/Very Eligible
Presentation	84.37	Very Valid/Very Eligible
Programming	95.83	Very Valid/Very Eligible
Contents	87.50	Very Valid/Very Eligible
Average score	89.14	Very Valid/Very Eligible

Table 5: Product Trial Table

IV. CONCLUSION

The results of the analysis conducted by researchers at Yamet Child Development Center Lampung are quite good for the development of Video Modeling learning media, due to the availability of adequate information and communication technology facilities and infrastructure. As well as teachers who are technology literate and have appropriate educational backgrounds and are qualified in using learning media based on computer technology and Android. The link between the potential and the conditions that occur, it is necessary to develop a Video Modeling learning media to improve self-development skills in dressing for mentally retarded children at the Yamet Child Development Center.

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded that the development of modeling video media is very appropriate to be used as a learning medium in learning to dress self-development. This can be seen from the results of the assessment of material experts worth 87.49 very decent categories, media experts worth 80.55 decent categories, and response tests and responses worth 89.14 very decent categories.

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